

Impact of Intermittent Fasting on Oral Health: A Narrative Review with Clinical Implications for Dental Management

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ABSTRACT— Intermittent fasting(IF) has gained popularity as a lifestyle approach for a better health, but its effects on oral health has been less studied and clearly understood. Fasting is associated with reduced salivary flow, changes in its composition, altered oral microflora and increased risk of plaque accumulation. At the same time, a lower frequency of food intake may reduce exposure to fermentable carbohydrates, thereby reducing the risk of dental caries. IF also has a beneficial effect on periodontal health by lowering oxidative stress and systemic inflammation. However, these effects are not consistent across all individuals and are influenced by diet, hydration and oral hygiene practices during non-fasting period. Most of the existing research is often focussed on specific type of fasting, which makes it difficult to generalize the findings. Overall, IF appears to have both beneficial and adverse effects on oral health, highlighting the need for further well-designed clinical research. This narrative review explores the effects of IF on oral health and also discusses the clinical implications for oral health professionals, highlighting practical strategies such as patient education, preventive care and personalised treatment planning to manage individuals who practice IF.

KEYWORDS —Dental caries, Intermittent fasting, Halitosis, Oral health, Periodontal health, Salivary flow, Xerostomia

I. INTRODUCTION

Intermittent fasting (IF) implies to a eating pattern that alternates between periods of food intake and voluntary abstinence from food in a restricted period of time. Common fasting windows include 14:10, 16:8 hours, one meal a day(OMAD) and alternate day fasting. Some practice religious fasting such as Ramadaan, Lent days, ekadaashi and weekly fasting based on deity and planets. Lately, fasting has drawn a lot of attention due to its potential benefits for weight control, better metabolic regulation and a possible reduction in inflammation and risk of chronic diseases.[1] Although the systemic effects of IF have been widely studied, its impact on oral health has not been explored to the same extent. Oral health is closely linked to dietary habits, salivary components and regulation and microbial balance within the oral cavity. Saliva plays a critical role in maintaining oral homeostasis and alterations in the flow and composition predisposes to dental caries, periodontal disease and various oral mucosal disorders.[2] Fasting changes the pH and flow of the saliva including the biochemical composition. Researches on Ramadaan intermittent fasting indicate that salivary flow tends to decrease causing dry mouth and halitosis. [3] Additionally, variations in salivary biomarkers and inflammatory mediators during fasting suggest a more complex link between the body's metabolic state and oral health. [4] That said, there may also be some potential benefits of IF. Reduced meal frequency decreases the exposure of teeth to fermentable carbohydrates, thereby reducing the risk of dental caries. Some recent studies also report that IF supports periodontal health by reducing systemic inflammation and altering the periodontal microbiota.[5] Despite the increasing amount of research, the available literature is still somewhat scattered and there are only a few comprehensive reviews that address the oral health implications of IF. Most of the existing literature comes from observational studies, predominantly based on specific fasting practices like Ramadaan fasting, which makes it difficult to apply the findings more broadly. Therefore, bringing the existing evidence together in a clear and understanding way is important for both clinicians and researchers. This narrative review, therefore, aims to bring together the existing literature on intermittent fasting and its effects on oral health, and to discuss its practical relevance for everyday dental practice.

II. OVERVIEW OF INTERMITTENT FASTING

Intermittent fasting refers to a food intake pattern which is practiced in many ways, each differing in duration and frequency of voluntary fasting. Rather than emphasizing on what to eat, IF primarily focusses on when to eat. Over the years, IF has gained considerable attention as a sustainable and practical approach in managing bodyweight and improving metabolic health. [6,7] IF can be followed in few different ways, depending on how long and how often an individual chooses to fast. One of the most common method is the 'time restricted feeding(TRF)', where food intake is limited to a set window each day. The

eating is limited usually around 6 to 10 hours, while fasting is maintained for the rest of the hours in the day setting a 18:6, 16:8 or 14:10 pattern.[7] Another pattern of IF is 'alternate day fasting(ADF)' where there is switching between days of unrestricted eating and days when calorie intake is significantly reduced. Additionally, periodic fasting such as the 5:2 diet where the individual consumes food normally for five days a week and restricts calories on two consecutive days[8] or the 'one meal a day(OMAD)' pattern.

The physiological changes seen with intermittent fasting are often explained by "metabolic switch". In the eating period, the body mainly relies on glucose from the dietary carbohydrates for energy. In the fasting window, as the fasting prolongs glycogen stores begin to deplete, and the body shifts to using fatty acids and ketone bodies and ketosis sets in.[7,9] This shift is associated with better insulin sensitivity, increased fat utilization and decreased circulating glucose levels. And also, a positive influence is seen in reduced blood pressure, improved lipid profiles and in reduction of inflammatory markers. [8, 10] At the cellular level, intermittent fasting facilitates autophagy, where the body removes damaged cellular components and promotes repair.[9] Despite these potential benefits, IF is not without challenges. Individuals response to fasting can vary based on factors such as age, gender, overall health, and how consistently the IF is followed. Some individuals may experience adverse effects like fatigue, weakness, irritability or dehydration especially during the early phase of adaptation.[8] From an oral health perspective, prolonged periods without fluid intake may reduce salivary flow, leading to dryness of the mouth and possible effects on oral tissues.

III. EFFECTS ON SALIVARY PHYSIOLOGY

Saliva plays a very important role in maintaining the oral health by its properties of lubrication, buffering capacity, digestion and taste enhancement and antimicrobial defense. Any changes in the quantity or quality of saliva can significantly affect the oral health. Salivary secretion is stimulated mainly by mastication and gustatory stimulus, fasting in IF can lead to decreased salivary flow due to absence of stimulation and dehydration[3] leading to decreased natural cleansing action of saliva, leading to plaque accumulation. Changes in the buffering capacity of saliva has been observed during fasting. The reduced pH creates an acidic oral environment which may favour tooth demineralization and microorganism growth. [11]

Various researches have assessed the effects of fasting on the biochemical composition of saliva. Changes in the proteins, enzymes, electrolyte content, amylase, immunoglobulins and various antimicrobial peptides in saliva may imbalance the ability to control microbial growth and maintain oral health.[5] In addition, fasting appears to fluctuate salivary cytokines and inflammatory markers suggesting a link between systemic metabolic shift and local immune responses in the oral cavity.[7] These changes can collectively increase the susceptibility of the oral cavity to changes and diseases, especially when fasting is prolonged or hydration is inadequate in IF. Table I shows the salivary changes and their clinical effects during intermittent fasting.

IV. IMPACT ON DENTAL CARIES

Dental caries is a multifactorial disease closely associated to dietary habits, particularly the frequency of carbohydrate intake. Repeated and prolonged exposure to fermentable carbohydrates facilitates acidogenic bacteria, especially *Streptococcus mutans* and *Lactobacillus* species to form acids from carbohydrates which result in decrease pH and subsequent demineralization of the tooth.[12,13] In IF the eating window and the frequency is invariably reduced, which means the teeth are exposed to sugars and other fermentable dietary components less frequently. With lesser eating frequency, the chances of acid production are less, allowing more time for saliva mediated remineralization between meals.[14] However, dietary habits during the eating window in IF plays a crucial role. If individuals consume high sugar or sticky foods within a short time period, it may counteract the benefits of reduced frequency of food intake. And also, during fasting periods, a reduced salivary flow is often observed which can inhibit remineralization and increase dental caries risk. [15] As a result, even with fewer acid interactions, the oral environment may become less conducive to remineralization of the enamel. Oral hygiene practices such as brushing, flossing and use of mouthwash can influence the risk of dental caries.

Current literature evidence on IF and dental caries is restricted and inconsistent as most of the studies are observational and focus on religious Ramadan fasting, which may not fully represent other forms of IF. Some studies report no significant increase in the caries incidence while others report the potential risks associated with poor oral hygiene and dehydration during fasting.[3,1] Therefore, the overall effect of IF on dental caries may depend on individual dietary choices during the eating window and their oral hygiene practices.

V. PERIODONTAL HEALTH AND INFLAMMATION

Periodontal diseases are chronic inflammatory conditions that is influenced by both local and systemic factors. The progression from simple gingivitis to more severe periodontitis is mainly due to an exaggerated inflammatory response to subgingival plaque, which eventually leads to damage of the supporting periodontal complex.[16] Because inflammation plays a major role in periodontal health, lifestyle factors such as IF are now being studied extensively for their possible role in periodontal health. Recent studies suggest that IF may have a beneficial effect on overall periodontal health by reducing systemic inflammation as well as by influencing the composition of subgingival microbiota leading to a healthier microbial balance in the periodontal complex.[5] Inflammatory markers like C-reactive protein, interleukin-6 and Tumor necrosis factor- α are known to be involved in periodontal disease. Studies have reported lower levels of these inflammatory markers in IF

thereby promoting decreased gingival inflammation and slower tissue damage.[10,8] Beyond its systemic effects, IF is also known to influence gingival inflammation. Studies on saliva and gingival crevicular fluid have reported changes in cytokine levels during fasting. [5] A reduction in the cytokine levels could mean less gingival bleeding, reduced periodontal pocket inflammation and an overall improvement in the periodontal health.

Another important aspect to be considered is oxidative stress, which plays a very vital role in periodontal tissue damage. IF has been associated with improved antioxidant capacity and lower levels of oxidative stress markers.[8] which may protect the periodontal tissues and enhance its anti-inflammatory effects. Changes in eating patterns can affect the availability of nutrients for oral microorganisms, thereby limiting the growth of harmful microorganisms and complementing a balanced microbial environment.[17] However, this benefit can be potentially neutralized by reduced salivary flow during fasting leading to plaque buildup. Despite these positive findings and effects of fasting, the evidence is still limited. Behavioural changes during fasting is also an important aspect that needs attention. Individuals may change their routine of oral hygiene, meal timings and hydration habits leading to plaque accumulation and risk of gingival and periodontal inflammation. Few studies report improvements in periodontal health indicators, while others show little to no change, suggesting that results can vary.[5,3] Differences in individual factors make it difficult to draw definite conclusions.

VI. HALITOSIS AND XEROSTOMIA

Halitosis and xerostomia are among the most commonly reported oral effects of IF, especially when fasting over an extended time without food or water. During fasting, particularly when fluid intake is time restricted, the flow of saliva often reduces.[3,1] Reduced salivary flow, changes in the oral microflora and metabolic activity that occur during fasting are known to cause these conditions. This mainly occurs due to the decreased stimulation of the salivary glands due to absence of eating along with added dehydration during the fasting period. The effects of decreased salivary flow during IF can be many. The natural cleansing mechanism of the oral cavity is hampered, allowing the accumulation of food debris and microorganisms. It also reduces the availability of calcium and phosphate ions needed for tooth remineralization. These factors increase the susceptibility of the tooth to dental caries.[15] In addition, reduced salivary flow can cause discomfort while speaking and during mastication, altered taste sensation, mucosal irritation and increase opportunistic infections such as candidiasis. These effects of IF may vary depending on various factors such as individual body physiology, duration of fasting, hydration during the fasting and non-fasting period and environmental changes. While these changes are often temporary and reversible, repeated or prolonged fasting without adequate care may have a cumulative effects on oral health.

Oral malodour or halitosis in IF primarily is caused as a result of reduced salivary flow due to the production of volatile sulphur compounds(VSCs) such as hydrogen sulphide and methyl mercaptan by increased activity of anaerobic bacteria in the oral cavity.[1,18] In addition, changes in the metabolism during the fasting period also plays a major role in oral malodour. During prolonged fasting in IF, the body shifts from glucose metabolism to fat metabolism producing ketone bodies such as acetone. These compounds can be released through breath, giving a characteristic “fruity” or acetone-like odour.[10] Other contributing factors during fasting include changes in oral hygiene habits, tongue coating especially the dorsum which can trap bacteria and debris, resulting in VSC production and resultant malodour.

VII. CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

With the increasing popularity of IF as a lifestyle, dental health professionals are more likely to see patients who follow various fasting patterns. Being aware of its possible effects on oral health helps clinicians offer a patient focused treatment and manage or prevent complications effectively.

A. Patient Assessment

A detailed history taking including questions about the fasting habits, such as type of fasting, duration and how often they follow the pattern should be noted. Clinicians should also understand their hydration habits, dietary choices during non fasting hours and how consistently they maintain their oral hygiene.[19] This helps identify patients at higher risk of oral complications such as xerostomia, halitosis, or increased plaque accumulation.

B. Oral Hygiene Recommendations

To maintain an optimum oral hygiene, patients can be advised to brush at least twice a day preferably after the pre-fasting food intake and before sleep, to use a fluoridated toothpaste for enamel remineralization, to use floss or interdental brushes and to incorporate tongue cleaning in everyday oral hygiene practice. Using an alcohol free mouthwash can also help keep the oral cavity fresh without adding to dryness of mucosa.[20]

C. Management of Xerostomia

For patients with xerostomia, simple measures can make a noticeable difference in the comfort of the patient. Patients should be advised and encouraged to stay well hydrated and avoid or limit caffeine, tobacco and alcohol during non fasting hours. Sugar free chewing gum or lozenges during the eating period may help stimulate salivary flow. Clinicians may consider prescribing saliva stimulating agents in severe cases.[21]

D. Dietary Advice

Dietary habits during the eating window plays a vital role in the caries status of the patient. Limiting frequent intake of sugary and sticky foods should be discouraged, especially late night snacking without brushing. For individuals at higher caries risk, preventive measures such as topical fluoride application and pit and fissure sealant can be considered to provide additional protection.[22]

E. Management of Halitosis

During IF, halitosis requires a combination of oral hygiene measures and management of underlying causes. Patients should be advised to clean the posterior part of the tongue regularly, as this area tends to retain debris and bacteria responsible for malodour. Short term use of antimicrobial mouthwash can be considered. Patients should be reassured that mild halitosis during fasting is relatively common and usually temporary.[23]

VIII. TIMING OF DENTAL APPOINTMENTS

For patients who follow IF, some adjustments are necessary to ensure patient comfort and safety. Whenever possible, appointments should be scheduled during non fasting hours, as patients are better hydrated, comfortable and are more able to tolerate dental procedures. If the patient has to be treated during the fasting hours, it is advisable to avoid extensive and time consuming procedures as patients may experience fatigue, dehydration and irritability to cope with longer treatment time. For patients requiring urgent care, clinicians should aim a well planned brief visit with adequate breaks, ensuring the patient remains comfortable throughout the procedure. Adapting appointments and treatment approaches taking the IF lifestyle of the patient can help improve patient compliance, comfort and overall clinical outcomes. [24]

IX. PATIENT EDUCATION AND COUNSELLING

Patient education and awareness plays a major role in reducing the oral health risks associated with IF. Clinicians should explain the effects of fasting on oral health in an easy to understand method, especially about reduced salivary flow and increased risk of mucosal irritation, periodontitis and dental caries. Dental health professionals should personalise their advice based on the patient's fasting pattern, duration and lifestyle making it more practical and easy to follow.

X. SPECIAL CONSIDERATIONS

Patients with systemic diseases and on medications such as diabetes, hypertension or elderly patients may already be experiencing xerostomia, fasting may aggravate the existing oral and systemic conditions. Similarly, individuals with a high index of dental caries and periodontitis need closer monitoring. Reduced salivary flow in addition to varied dietary choices during the non fasting hours, may accelerate the progression of these conditions if preventive measures are not incorporated. In such instances, a more cautious and individualized treatment approach is needed. Clinicians may need to strategize the treatment planning, recommend more frequent followups and if necessary coordinate with the patient's physician to help balance the patient's oral health needs with their personal or cultural practices.[25]

XI. CONCLUSION

Worldwide, IF is becoming popular for its overall health benefits, but its effects on oral health are mixed and depend on multiple factors. While there maybe some benefits, they are often balanced by potential drawbacks. Since most of the available literature is limited and mainly observational, highlighting more well-designed studies to understand the long term impact of IF on oral health.

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